

Gimnastikaning sport turlari va sog'lomlashtiruvchi ahamiyati.

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Anatatsiya: *Jismoniy tarbiyada umumiy jismoniy rivojlanish va insonning asosiy motor qobiliyatlarini yaxshilashni ta'minlaydigan gimnastika alohida o'rin tutadi. Gimnastika turli xil mashqlar bilan ajralib turadi, bu aniqlarni eng muvaffaqiyatli hal qilish uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratadi*

Kalit so'zlar: *Gimnastika, sog'lomlashtirish, saf mashqlari, sakrash, erkin mashq, akrobatika, xoreografiya.*

Gimnastikaning sport turlariga gimnastika, badiiy gimnastika, sport akrobatikasi kiradi, sport aerobikasi va fitnes aerobikasi.

Gimnastika ko'pkurashning bir nechta turlarini o'z ichiga oladi. Bunga quyidagilar kiradi: erkaklarda-bepul mashqlar, mashqlar otda, halqalarda, barlarda, barda, qo'llab-quvvatlovchi sakrashlar; ayollarda-qo'llab-quvvatlash sakrashlari, turli balandlikdagi barlarda mashqlar, gimnastika logida va polda mashqlar. Darslarga badiiy gimnastika badiiy mashqlarni o'z ichiga oladi gimnastika, xoreografiya, akrobatika.

Sport gimnastikasi – Olimpiya sport turi. Mamlakatimizda uning rivojlanishiga rahbarlik qiladi gimnastikasi federatsiyasi.

Badiiy gimnastika-bu sof ayol sport turi.

Uning asosiy vositalari klassik raqs, ritm, plastmassa elementlari, ob'ektlar bilan bajariladigan raqs mashqlari (halqa, arqon, lenta, to'p, klublar) va ob'ektlarsiz, albatta musiqiy hamrohlik. Badiiy gimnastika ham Olimpiya sport turi hisoblanadi va uning mamlakatimizda rivojlanishi badiiy gimnastika Federatsiyasi tomonidan boshqariladi.

Sport akrobatikasi uchta mashq guruhini o'z ichiga oladi: akrobatik sakrash, juftlik (erkak va aralash juftliklar), guruh mashqlari va trambolin mashqlari. Keng akrobatik mashqlarning murakkabligi diapazoni ularni yoshi, jinsi va jismoniy tayyorgarligi jihatidan farq qiladigan shaxslarga o'rgatish imkonini beradi. U turli miqyosdagi musobaqalarni tashkil qiladi va o'tkazadi.

Sport aerobikasi-bu sport turi sportchilar uzluksiz va yuqori samarali mashqlar to'plami, shu jumladan murakkab koordinatsion asiklik harakatlarning kombinatsiyasi, turli xil tarkibiy guruhlarning turli xil murakkab elementlari, shuningdek sheriklar o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sir. Tarkibi quyidagi fanlardan: erkaklarning individual chiqishlari va ayollar, har qanday tarkibdagi aralash juftliklar, uchlik va oltitalar. Ushbu mashqlarda

xoreografiyaning asosini quyidagilar tashkil etadi aerobik qadamlar va ularning birikmalari.

Fitness aerobikasi-bu jamoaviy murakkab muvofiqlashtirilgan doimiy sport bilan ajralib turadigan asiklik sport klassik aerobikaga xos harakatlarni bajarish

yuqori intensivlik, Step-aerobika, musiqaga ijro etiladigan hip-hop uslubidagi aerobikaning raqs turi. 1995 yilda xalqaro Olimpiya qo'mitasi (XOQ) tomonidan aerobika rasmiy intizom deb tan olindi va xalqaro gimnastika federatsiyasiga kirdi.

Fitness aerobikasini rivojlantirish va ommalashtirish bilan FISAF xalqaro tashkiloti shug'ullanadi, Prezident Stefan Bartelemy (Fransiya), Rossiyada esa Rossiya fitnes – aerobika Federatsiyasi, uning prezidenti Olga Slutsker. Chempionatlar o'tkaziladi jahon va Yevropa, xalqaro turnirlar va bolalar, o'smirlar va kattalar o'rtasida Umumrusiya musobaqalari. Musobaqa dasturi uchta fanni o'z ichiga oladi:

- ✓ aerobika;
- ✓ qadam aerobikasi;
- ✓ hip-hop

Gimnastikaning sog'lomlashtirish turlari.

Gimnastikaning sog'lomlashtirish turlari ertalabki gigiena (jismoniy mashqlar) va kirish gimnastikasi, jismoniy tarbiya, o'quv muassasalarida, ishlab chiqarishda jismoniy tarbiya shaklida mashqlarni bajarishni o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu guruhga terapevtik ham kiradi gimnastika. Ularning asosiy maqsadi salomatlikni mustahkamlashdir inson, o'qish, ishda jismoniy va aqliy faoliyatini yuqori darajada ushlab turish, faollikni oshirish mehnat va ijtimoiy faoliyatda Gigienik gimnastika inson salomatligini mustahkamlash va saqlash, umuman tananing hayotiy faoliyatini oshirish muammolarini hal qiladi. Fiziologik ta'sir nuqtai nazaridan gigienik gimnastika tinglovchilarning butun tanasini tonlaydi va engillashtiradi insonning mehnat va ijtimoiy foydali faoliyatidan keyin umumiy charchoq Gigienik gimnastika insonning kundalik hayotida keng qo'llaniladi. Bu odamda yaxshi odatlarni tarbiyalashga yordam beradi: gigiena qoidalariga rioya qilish, muntazam jismoniy mashqlar bilan tanishish. Gigienik gimnastika ertalab, tushdan keyin va kechqurun o'tkazilishi mumkin. Ertalab gimnastika tananing optimal ishlashiga tezda erishish uchun ishlatiladi; kun davomida mashqlar charchoqni oldini olish yoki bartaraf etish, qarshi turish uchun amalga oshiriladi kundalik gipokineziyaning salbiy ta'siri; kechki mashg'ulotlar kunduzgi stressni engillashtirishga yordam beradi, foydali ta'sir ko'rsatadi keyingi uyqu uchun. Barcha holatlarda jismoniy mashqlarni qattiqlashuv protseduralari bilan birlashtirish tavsiya etiladi.

Sog'lomlashtiruvchi gimnastikasi insonlarni mehnat faoliyatiga tezda jalb qilishga qaratilgan. Tashkilot shaklida bu maktabda "darsdan oldin gimnastika"va" ishdan oldin gimnastika". Bu erda mashqlar tuzilishda qo'llaniladi harakatlar, energiya va hissiy

ta'minot yaqin professional vosita harakatlariga. Jismoniy mashqlar paytida fiziologik va psixologik erishiladi faol va yuqori samarali o'quv va ishlab chiqarish faoliyatiga munosabat. Ijro muddati jismoniy mashqlar-5-10 daqiqa.

Jismoniy tarbiya yoki jismoniy tarbiya, jismoniy va aqliy ko'rsatkichlarni yuqori darajada ushlab turish uchun ishlatiladi butun maktab yoki ish kuni davomida daraja, duruq buzilishining oldini olish, mahalliy jismoniy charchoq. U o'quv mashg'ulotlari yoki ish paytida charchoq belgilari (chalg'itish, holatni buzish, charchoq hissi va boshqalar) paydo bo'lganda amalga oshiriladi. Kompleks 5-10 ta mashqdan iborat bo'lib, 2-5 daqiqa ichida bajarilishi mumkin. Terapevtik gimnastika terapevtik jismoniy madaniyatning asosidir (jismoniy mashqlar terapiyasi). Bu shikastlanish, shikastlanish, kasallik, jarrohlik va boshqalardan keyin tananing vaqtincha yo'qolgan individual funktsiyalarini tiklashga yordam beradi. U turli xil kasalliklar uchun boshqa dorilar bilan birgalikda ishlatiladi, ammo ayniqsa, mushak-skelet tizimini davolashda samarali. Darsning asosiy shakli-bu 30-60 daqiqa davom etadigan dars yoki protsedura. Terapevtik jismoniy madaniyatning bir turi-bu sog'liqni saqlashning noan'anaviy turlari gimnastika: tuzatish, dam olish, tiklash, nafas olish, artikulyar va boshqalar.

Foydalangan adabiyotlar

1. Sayfiyev Hikmatullo Xayrulloevich. (2023). Sport gimnastika mashg'ulotlarida asosiy harakat qobilyat (FMS), postural (muvozanat) nazorat va o'zini o'zi idrok etishga sport gimnastikasining ta'sir. *Oriental Journal of Academic and Multidisciplinary Research* , 1(3), 74-81.
2. Sayfiyev Hikmatullo Xayrulloevich. (2023). Acrobat exercise and sports gymnastika sessions through the power of development method. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 460–467.
3. Sayfiyev Hikmatullo Xayrulloevich. (2023). Methods and methods of teaching sports gymnastics in young boles. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 453–459.
4. Xayrulloevich, S. H. (2023). Use of Acrobatic Exercises and Their Terms In The Process of Teaching Gymnastics. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies* (2993-2599), 1 (9), 80–86.
5. Sayfiyev Hikmatullo Xayrulloevich. (2023). AEROBIK GIMNASTIKANING XUSUSIYATLARI. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 442–448.
6. Sayfiyev Hikmatullo Xayrulloevich. (2023). SPORTS ARE GYMNASTICS IN ACTION SERIES-BE THE MANIFESTATION OF COME. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 465–477. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/~niverta1/index.php/tsru/article/view/3587>

VOLUME-2, ISSUE-1

7. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). РАЗВИТИЕ ДВИЖИТЕЛЬНЫХ НАВЫКОВ ДЕТЕЙ МЛАДШЕГО ВОЗРАСТА С ПОМОЩЬЮ СПОРТИВНОЙ ГИМНАСТИКИ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА КАК ИЗ. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 457–464.
8. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). Norms of gymnasiums and activities of gymnasiums. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 428–434.
9. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). SPORT GIMNASTIKASIDA HARAKATLAR KETMA-KELIGINING NAMOYON VO'LISHI. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 478–491
10. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). АЭРОБНОЙ ГИМНАСТИКИ. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 449–456.
11. Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). Sportda murabbiylik faoliyatining psixologik tadqiqoti. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 344-352.
12. Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg 'ulotlari sog 'lom turmush tarzining ajralmas qismidir. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 338-343.
13. Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). Harakat malakalarini shakllantirishning fiziologik asoslari va sport texnikasini o 'rgatish. E'tiqod va madaniyatning kesishgan joylari: Amerika diniy va madaniyat tadqiqotlari jurnali (2993-2599), 1(9), 87-94.
14. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Physical attributes (capabilities) of development of the main legality. Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies, 2(12), 373–380.
15. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). СОЗДАНИЕ ПРОГРАММЫ ДЛЯ ИМИТАЦИИ ШИФРОВАНИЯ МАШИНЫ ENIGMA НА ЯЗЫКЕ PYTHON. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 317-323.
16. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). STUDY THE PSYCHOLOGY OF PROGRAMMERS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 563-568.
17. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Physical attributes (capabilities) of development of the main legality. Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies, 2(12), 373–380.
18. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Psychological Research Of Coaching Activities In Sports. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 344–352. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPDIS/article/view/1565>

VOLUME-2, ISSUE-1

19. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Jismoniy qobiliyatlarning rivojlanishi va jismoniy sifatlarning ko'chishi. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 379–393. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/tsru/article/view/3554>
20. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Physical downloads and the rest of fulfilling exercise mutual dependence. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 394–409. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/~niverta1/index.php/tsru/article/view/3556>
21. Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich Sayfiev. (2023). The Place of Gymnastics in A Person's Life and the Terms Used in Training. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 353–359. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPDIS/article/view/1566>
22. Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). The Initial Exercise of Teaching Methodology to Gymnastics . American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 329–337. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPDIS/article/view/1563>
23. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). PHYSIOLOGICAL REACTIONS TO INTERNAL LOAD STUDY. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(12), 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-07>
24. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). SPORTS PEDAGOGY BASED ON PSYCHOMOTOR AND DEVELOPMENT THEORIES. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(12), 26–41. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-05>
25. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). SPORTS, CULTURE AND SOCIETY. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 152–163. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-17>
26. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). FOCUS ON AEROBIC (LI) TYPE OF MOTOR ACTIVITY BASED ON FITNESS PROGRAMS. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 81–90.
27. Yarasheva Dilnoza. (2023). METHODS OF ORGANIZING NON-TRADITIONAL FITNESS CLASSES. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 61–72. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-09>
28. Yarasheva Dilnoza Ismail Qizi. (2023). TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL SKILLS IN SPORTS. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(10), 105–116. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue10-16>
29. Yarashova, D. (2023). THE IMPACT OF PLAYING SPORTS IN EARLY CHILDHOOD ON SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT. Modern Science and Research, 2(10),

230–234. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24325>

30. Ярашева, Д. (2023, April). ФИТНЕС КАК ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ. In Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies (Vol. 2, No. 4, pp. 278-283).

31. Yarasheva, D. (2022). BOLALARDA MASHQ QILISHNING ANAMIYATI. PEDAGOGS jurnali, 19(1), 139-142.

32. Ярашева, Д. (2023). СТИЛИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ НЕТРАДИЦИОННЫХ ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 19(5), 6-10.

33. Yarashova, D. (2023). STRENGTH TRAINING AND STRENGTH TRAINING IN CHILDREN. Modern Science and Research, 2(9), 211-215.

34. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). APPROACHES, BEHAVIORAL CHARACTERISTICS, PRINCIPLES AND METHODS OF WORK OF COACHES AND MANAGERS IN SPORTS. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 133–151. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-16>

35. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). GLOBALIZATION AND SPORTS INDUSTRY. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 164–182. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-18>

36. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). SOCIAL SPORTS MARKETING. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(12), 121–134. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-17>

37. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). RECOVERY STRATEGY IN SPORTS. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(12), 135–147. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-18>

38. Azamat Orunbayev, (2023) NONUSHTANING MASHQ BAJARISHGA TA'SIRI. International journal of scientific researchers 2(2), 3-6.

39. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). USING TECHNOLOGY IN A SPORTS ENVIRONMENT. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 39–49. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-07>

40. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). FITNES VA SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH BO'YICHA MURABBIYLIK YO'NALISHIGA KONTSEPTUAL YONDASHUV. Research Focus International Scientific Journal, 2(8), 23–28. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/431>

41. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). PANDEMIYA DAVRIDA MOBIL SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH VA FITNES DASTURLARI (PROGRAM). Research Focus International Scientific Journal, 2(7), 37–42. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/414>

VOLUME-2, ISSUE-1

42. Akhrorjon Nuriddinov. (2023). A STUDY OF THE AGGRESSIVE STATUS OF FOOTBALL FANS. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 73–80. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-10>

43. Bahodir o'g'li, N. A. (2023). YEVIROPA MAMLAKATLARIDA YUQORI MALAKALI FUTBOLCHI VA MURABBIYLARNI TEXNIK TAKTIK HARAKATLARINI TADBIQ QILISH METODIKASI. THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH, 2(14), 187-189.

44. Nuriddinov, A., Sayfiyev, H., & Sirojev, S. . (2023). WHY FOOTBALL IS THE FIRST SPORT THAT COMES TO MIND TODAY. Modern Science and Research, 2(9), 200–203. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24104>

45. Nuriddinov, A. (2023). THE ROLE OF FAIR PLAY IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION. Modern Science and Research, 2(10), 244–250. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24327>

46. Bahodir o'g'li, N. A. (2023). NIMA UCHUN FUTBOL BUGUNGI KUNDA SPORT DEB ATALGANIDA BIRINCHI NAVBATDA AQLGA KELADI.

47. Nuriddinov Axrorjon Bahodir o'g'li, (2023) Futbol zo'ravonligi, fanatizm va millatchilik International journal of scientific researchers 2(1), 451-456.

48. Akhrorjon Nuriddinov. (2023). USE OF DIGITAL SPORTS TECHNOLOGIES IN SPORTS TELEVISION. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 208–219. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-22>

49. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). BEHAVIORAL CHARACTERISTICS, PRINCIPLES AND WORKING METHODS OF COACHES. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 3(11), 50–60. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-08>